

Importance of धर्मशास्त्र and Its Reflection in the Present-Day Society

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One of the fundamental principles of religion is that we should perform our duties with piety and to the best of our ability, without any attachment or concern for the results. The श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता also says that by grasping धर्म, we need to master our mind and senses to follow the right rules. By following धर्म, we can purify our mind as well as heart, advance on the spiritual path, and attain fulfillment in life. A disciplined mind is always capable of making wise decisions.

धर्म is the path to permanent peace and happiness. The second chapter of the श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता states that “the self-controlled man, freed from attraction and repulsion by restraining the senses and moving among objects, attains true peace.” It also says, “There can be no peace to a mindless man; and who does not have peace, how is it possible to be happy?”

The Sanskrit स्मृतिशास्त्र or धर्मशास्त्र emphasizes the universal धर्म principles of truthfulness, non-violence, duty, justice, compassion, and integrity, which creates a clear link between spirituality and ethics and paves the way to liberation. Those who possess and actualize these qualities are characterized by divine qualities that enable them to rationalize their human existence and progress toward liberation.

The स्मृतिशास्त्र or धर्मशास्त्र plays a crucial part in the lives of humans. The two guides for human beings to follow the correct path in actual life are the Vedas and स्मृतिशास्त्र “श्रुतिस्मृति चक्षुषी द्वे.” Many laws and rules are created in tandem with societal growth to ensure that individuals can live in a prosperous and healthy society. These guidelines are all contained in the स्मृतिशास्त्र, also known as धर्मशास्त्र. Social structures and laws are modified in response to public requirements. The contemporary world and the previous system are very different from one another. The purpose of this study is to give specific examples of how the धर्मशास्त्र descriptions of modern societal harmony and culture might be applied today.

In स्मृतिशास्त्र or धर्मशास्त्र human relations topics are included in addition to casteism's depiction. Everyone must work together to achieve the society's overall development. Reminding the aged, destitute, and illiterate of their frailty should not be construed as an insult. There are several examples in our culture of disabled people achieving their goals when they are supported and given enough chances. This is why the writers of स्मृतिशास्त्र or धर्मशास्त्र are requesting everyone's cooperation.

Thirty characteristics of the धर्म have been mentioned in the Seventh Canto of श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता and these श्लोक are carried great importance in our Society.

सत्यं दया तपः शौचं तितिक्षेक्षा शमो दमः।

अहिंसा ब्रह्मचर्यं च त्यागः स्वाध्याय आर्जवम्॥

संतोषः समदृक् सेवा ग्राम्येहोपरमः शनैः।

नृणां विपर्ययेहेक्षा मौनमात्मविमर्शनम्॥

अन्नाद्यादे संविभागो भूतेभ्यश्च यथार्हतः।

तेषात्मदेवताबुद्धिः सुतरां नृषु पाण्डव॥

श्रवणं कीर्तनं चास्य स्मरणं महतां गतेः।

सेवेज्यावनतिर्दास्यं सख्यमात्मसमर्पणम्॥

नृणामयं परो धर्मः सर्वेषां समुदाहृतः।
त्रिशल्लक्षणवान् राजन् सर्वात्मा येन तुष्यति॥¹

आचार्य मनु has enumerated ten characteristics of धर्मः

धृतिः क्षमा दमोऽस्तेयं शौचमिन्द्रियनिग्रहः।
धीर्विद्या सत्यमक्रोधो दशकं धर्मलक्षणम्॥²

याज्ञवल्क्य मनु has enumerated nine characteristics of धर्मः

अहिंसा सत्यमस्तेयं शौचमिन्द्रियनिग्रहः।
दानं दमो दया शान्तिः सर्वेषां धर्मसाधनम्॥³

The Sanskrit धर्मशास्त्र मनुस्मृति states:

विद्वद्धिः सेवितः सद्धिर्नित्यमद्वेषरागिभिः ।
हृदयेनाभ्यनुज्ञातो यो धर्मस्तं निबोधत ॥⁴

Learn that धर्म, which has always been followed, and approved by the hearts of those, learned and good, who are free from love and hatred. So, in श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता श्रीकृष्ण said that:

यदा यदा हि धर्मस्य ग्लानिर्भवति भारत।
अभ्युत्थानमधर्मस्य तदात्मानं सृजाम्यहम्॥
परित्राणाय साधूनाम् विनाशाय च दुष्कृताम्।
धर्मसंस्थापनार्थाय सम्भवामि युगे युगे॥⁵

That is, whenever righteousness declines and unrighteousness increases, then I create my form, that is, I appear before people in physical form. I have

1. श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता, 7, श्लोक - 8 – 12.
2. मनुस्मृति, 6 - 12.
3. याज्ञवल्क्य स्मृति, 1 – 112
4. मनुस्मृति, 1 - 120
5. श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता, 4, श्लोक 7 – 8

6. मनुसंहिता, 1 – 141
7. विष्णुसंहिता, 71 – 2
8. याज्ञवल्क्यसंहिता, व्यवहाराध्याय – 237
9. मनुसंहिता 2 - 226

appeared in every age to save the righteous, destroy the sinners, and establish righteousness. Men have righteous and unrighteous instincts. Sometimes piety increases and sometimes irreligion. Therefore, Sanskrit धर्मशास्त्र needs ethical, religious, political, economic, socio-ethical, philosophical, spiritual, metaphysical, and meta-theological teaching of correct धर्म to sustain the society.

हीनाङ्गानतिरिक्ताङ्गान् विद्याहीनान्वयोऽधिकान्।

रूपद्रव्यविहीनांश्च जातिहीनांश्च निक्षिपेत्॥⁶

न च हीनाङ्गानाधिकाङ्गान् मूर्खान् धनहीनानि वहसेत्॥⁷

In our society today, there is virtually always outrage directed towards parents. In several instances about this issue, the judiciary has adopted a strict position. The petitioners, who are the parents of the molested children, are directing the local police officers to take the proper action. The ideas “मातृ देवो भव” and “पितृ देवो भव” are no longer prevalent in society. Still, the writers of स्मृतिशास्त्र have demonstrated social consciousness by mandating stringent actions in this regard. According to आचार्य मनु - पितरं मातरं न हिंस्यात् (मनुसंहिता ४/१६२)

Family members should never part from one another until circumstances worsen, stated to याज्ञवल्क्य. So याज्ञवल्क्य stated:

पितृपुत्रस्वसृभ्रातृदम्पत्याचार्यशिक्षकाः।

एषामपतितान्योन्यत्यागी च शतदण्डभाक्॥⁸

It is incredibly hard for parents to give birth and raise a child. According to the authors of स्मृतिशास्त्र or धर्मशास्त्र, the child will never be able to repay his parents' debt during his entire life. Parents most definitely do not want to dedicate their

later years to an assisted living facility after the struggles of becoming parents and raising a child. According to आचार्य मनु

यं मातापितरौ क्लेशं सहेते सम्भवे नृणाम्।

न तस्य निष्कृतिः शक्या कर्तुं वर्षशतैरपि।⁹

These days, the law must specify how capable children are to care for their aged parents. The “Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act 2007” is currently in effect. Currently, with the news filled with horrible stories of abusive parents, the guidance of the authors of स्मृतिशास्त्र or धर्मशास्त्र has brought attention to the beneficial elements of traditional Indian Culture. Elderly persons should be treated with kindness, according to the writers of स्मृतिशास्त्र or धर्मशास्त्र. These days, with the senior citizen bill in place and World elders' day, observed, it is not ideal for our forward-thinking civilization to stimulate the development of old age homes.

The writers of स्मृतिशास्त्र or धर्मशास्त्र came up with several ideas to address different societal issues. Their insightful thinking has helped society find solutions to many of its issues. Doctors currently advise getting prenatal care through Sishu Bikash Kendra, Matri Mangal Institute, etc. Even though the authors of स्मृतिशास्त्र or धर्मशास्त्र mentioned this idea ages ago. They advised regarding how to care for expecting wives and mothers,

दौहृदस्यप्रदानेन गर्भो दोषमवाप्नुयात्।

वैरूप्यं मरणं वाऽपि तस्मात् कार्यं प्रियं स्त्रियाः।।¹⁰

What penalty does the guilty party face? In this sense, the law's provision may be updated to reflect the evolving circumstances of the present. However, the

10. याज्ञवल्क्यसंहिता 3 – 89

11. मनुसंहिता 7 – 20

12. मनुसंहिता 7 – 198 – 199

13. रामायण – 1/1/47

way the accused is punished in both the ancient and modern legal systems is the same. The chapter on राजधर्म highlights आचार्य मनु's emphasis on penalizing offenders. The law requires the King to punish the transgressor appropriately. If inmates receive insufficient punishment, crime will persist throughout the entire state.

यदि न प्रणयेद्राजा दण्डं दण्डेष्वतन्द्रितः।

शूले मत्स्यानिवापक्ष्यन् दुर्बलान् बलवत्तराः॥¹¹

The war is fought in the context of the monarch's plan to subjugate the realm. Pain and destruction are the results of war. But people have the power to prevent it. Given the loss of a battle, आचार्य मनु advised the monarch to avoid conflict by implementing strategies like साम, दान, भेद, and दण्ड. This is critical to the advancement of society.

साम्ना दानेन भेदेन समस्तैरथवा पृथक्।

विजेतुं प्रयतेतारीन् न युद्धेन कदाचन।

अनित्यो विजयो यस्माद् दृश्यते युध्यमानयोः।

पराजयश्च संग्रामे तस्माद् युद्धं विवर्जयेत्॥¹²

Let's finally discuss environmental consciousness. Keeping a healthy, balanced environment in both social and ecological contexts is essential. The United Nations has declared June 5th to be Environment Day each year to provide nations with a pollution-free environment in which to live. The word 'Environment' comes from the word 'which surrounds us.' On the other side, pollution is a dangerous state that regresses society. The epic रामायण depicts:

ततः शूर्पणखावाक्याद् उद् युक्तान् सर्वराक्षसान्।

खरं त्रिशिरसं चैव दूषणं चैव राक्षसम्॥¹³

According to the metaphor, although the demon is harmful, it is also defeatable. Thus, it might be claimed that, just as the monster was vanquished in दण्डकारण्य ages ago, people will become aware of their surroundings now and will need to prevent pollution. आचार्य मनु reminded us of the 'Plant the Tree, Save the Life' or 'One Tree, One Life' campaigns. He asserted that trees experience both joy and sorrow throughout life.

अन्तः संज्ञा भवन्त्येते सुखदुःखसमन्विताः।¹⁴

Here, a few significant topics from the writers of स्मृतिशास्त्र or धर्मशास्त्र are examined in light of modern culture and society. In conclusion, it can be stated that the state and society will get stronger with human resources if the writers of स्मृतिशास्त्र or धर्मशास्त्र norms and regulations are adhered to. The goal of the authors of स्मृतिशास्त्र or धर्मशास्त्र was for other people to continuously learn valuable lessons of wealth from this place.

एतद्देशप्रसूतस्य सकाशादग्रजन्मनः।

स्वं स्वं चरित्रं शिक्षेरन् पृथिव्यां सर्वमानवाः।¹⁵

The Sanskrit स्मृतिशास्त्र or धर्मशास्त्र describes peace, compassion, modesty, and absence of hatred as qualities of a person with divine qualities. On the other hand, a person with the qualities of hypocrisy, arrogance, harshness, and anger is considered to be demonic and character.

The श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता explains that धर्म is a deep inner wisdom, and moral precepts that guide us to perform our duties, lead righteous lives and ultimately attain

14. मनुसंहिता 1/49

15. मनुसंहिता 2/20

16. महोपनिषद् – अध्याय-6, मन्त्र-71

17. अथर्ववेद – 19/15/6

18. शुक्लयजु - अध्याय संख्या-36. मन्त्रः संख्या-18

19. महोपनिषद् – अध्याय-6, मन्त्र-71

spiritual realization. Religion is not just a system of laws and customs. As stated in the श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता:

धारणात् धर्म इत्याहुः धर्मो धारयति प्रजाः ।
यः स्यात् धारणसंयुक्तः स धर्म इति निश्चयः ॥

In other words, the meaning of the word धर्म is that which holds the race is called धर्म, धर्म holds the people, and the rules which are associated with virtue are called धर्म. धर्म is not just a central concept such as Hindu, Muslim, Buddhist, or Jain, it is a detailed form that unites all and eliminates the separation. What can unite the entire society is धर्म.

‘सर्वेऽत्र सुखिनः सन्तु’, ‘वसुधैव कुटुम्बकम्’¹⁶

‘सर्वा आशा मम मित्रं भवन्तु’¹⁷, ‘मित्रस्य चक्षुषा सर्वाणि भूतानि समीक्षे’¹⁸

Our scriptures always try to initiate the human beings of our beautiful society in these मन्त्रs, by which our society can take a beautiful form. But the people of today's society are busy dividing this society by जाति, धर्म, and वर्ण. Our वैदिक मन्त्रs and नीति श्लोकs are eternally striving and propagating to bind this divided society back to the same thread -

अयं निजः परोवेति, गणना लघुचेतसाम्।

उदार चरितानां तु, वसुधैव कुटुम्बकम्॥¹⁹

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